

EFFECTS OF STACKING SEQUENCES ON THE HYDROELASTIC BEHAVIOR OF COMPOSITE PROPELLER BLADES

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SUMMARY: A finite element method coupled with analysis of a non-cavitating lifting surface was used to assess the performance of a composite marine propeller, including thrust, torque, efficiency coefficients and deflections. An MAU 3-60 propeller was analyzed with different stacking sequence of T300/1076E. The hydroelastic behavior of the propeller with balanced and unbalanced stacking sequences were investigated and discussed. Stacking sequences effects have been shown to influence the performance of composite propeller in region of low advanced coefficient, J.

INTRODUCTION

Hydrodynamic aspects of the design of a marine propeller attract attention for the purposes of predicting the deflection and strength of the propeller blade and increasing its efficiency. A procedure to calculate the blade strength must involve numerical methods because of the nonlinear phenomenon of the blade deflection and its loading. A geometrically non-linear calculation is needed to calculate the quasistatic deflection of the blade that results from the centrifugal force and the distribution of pressure in the fluid.

The first approach to solve the strength problem of the blade was proposed by Taylor[1], who considered a propeller blade to be a cantilever rigidly attached to a boss. The stresses were calculated with elementary beam theory using cylindrical blade sections having a straight face and a curved back. The cantilever beam theory yields reasonable estimates of stresses at certain selected points of relatively straight and narrow blades. Modified forms of this theory are proposed for a wide propeller blade, but limited knowledge of the structural response of the blade is available. The approach of shell theory was first proposed by Cohen[2], who considered a propeller blade to be a helicoid shell of variable thickness and infinite width. This approach was limited when applied to a blade of the finite width. Conolly[3] developed a thin-shell approach in parallel with an experimental program. This approach was demonstrated to be successful for a wide blade, but symmetrical forms and the assumption that the normal deflection of a section was invariant limited the application of the method. Moreover theories of shell type that incorporate broad assumption are involved for routine design work.

The reason to choose of the finite element method is its lack of any additional assumption about the behavior of the displacements. Genalis[4] used a triangular plane element and Atkinson[5] used a parabolic and curved element of a thick shell model to analyze the mathematically defined propeller. These results are compared with calculated and

experimental results presents by Conolly. The conclusion is that a thick-shell model is satisfactory to calculate the response of propeller blade. Ma[6] applied the isoparametric solid element model to analyze a highly skewed propeller the computed results are compared with measured deflections and stresses under a steady pressure. Sontvedt[7] applied a triangular thin-shell element to analyze moderately screwed and highly screwed propeller under hydrodynamic loading of frozen type. The calculated results of stresses and deflection are compared with experiments. Atkinson and Golver[8] applied a curved superparametric thick-shell element model to analyze three types of propellers. The surface loading was calculated according to a steady lifting surface analysis developed by Szantyr[9]. In this process, the surface pressure is first obtained on assuming that the structure is rigid and the resulting surface pressure is imposed on the structure to calculate the structural response. An iterative procedure is applied to calculate a new geometry of blade and to modify the surface loading. The process is repeated until a new stable condition is achieved. Thus this approach is applied in an uncoupled manner.

The developed procedure of the coupled fluid-structure analysis[10] was used in the evaluation of effects of stacking sequences on hydroelastic behavior of composite propeller blades. The geometrical non-linear finite element procedure for structural analysis and non-cavitating lifting surface theory for fluid analysis were considered. The Newton-Raphson procedure was used in the equation solver.

FLUID-STRUCTURE INTERACTION

The finite element equation for a geometrically non-linear three-dimensional degenerate shell element is written as

$$([K_o] + [K_L] + [K_G] - [K_R])\{u\} = \{F_{ext}\} + \{F_I\} + \{F_R\} = [K_T]\{u\} \quad (1)$$

in which $[K_o]$, $[K_L]$, $[K_G]$ and $[K_R]$ are the linear stiffness, initial displacement, geometric and rotational matrix, $\{u\}$ is the nodal displacement, $\{F_{ext}\}$ are the external forces excluding fluid forces $\{F_I\}$, $\{F_R\}$ are the centrifugal load.

The steady and noncavitating lifting surface analysis procedure used in the present work is that of Kerwin and Lee[11]. The strengths of the sources representing the blade thickness are pre-determined by a stripwise application of thin-wing theory at each radius, leaving only the vortex strengths to be determined. The horseshoe vortex strengths, Γ , on each blade can be expressed in terms of those on the key blade.

$$\sum_{j=1}^{(N \times M)} A_{ij} \Gamma_j = G(u) \Gamma_i = -\vec{n}_i \cdot (\vec{V}_\infty + \vec{V}_\Omega + \vec{V}_q^{source})_i = rhs(u) \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, N \times M \quad (2)$$

The forces of the fluid acting on the blades are expressed as:

$$F_I = \int_A N_s^T n N dA \cdot \{\Delta P\} = [B]\{\Gamma^{vortex}\} + \{C\} \quad (3)$$

In which, $[B]$ is the coupled matrix of interaction between fluid and structure, $[C]$ is the matrix determined from the distribution of the blade thickness of the blade that can be neglected if the thickness effects of the blades is ignored.

The finite-element equations (1) and (3) coupled with equation (2) is expressed as

$$\begin{bmatrix} K_T(u) & -B(u) \\ 0 & G(u) \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} u \\ \Gamma \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} F_R(u) + F_{ext} + C \\ rhs(u) \end{Bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

The Newton-Raphson method was used to solve these equations. Three convergence criteria was adopted in structural, the displacement, external forces and external work, and two in fluid, wake velocities just behind the trailing edge and the strength of the singularity, for every iteration.

NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

An MAU 3-60 propeller was analyzed. The MAU 3-60 propeller has three blades as shown in Fig. 1. Its expansion ratio is 0.6, diameter D is 150 cm. Table 1 shows geometrical data of the MAU 3-60 propeller. The generation line of propeller blade is taken as the reference of fiber direction θ of composites. The fiber from root to the leading edge is positive. Two stacking sequences $[0/90/\theta_2]_s$ and $[0/90/-\theta_2]_s$ were considered. The number of layer was account for from middle surface to upper and lower surface of propeller blades. Thus different location has different number of layers.

Table 1: The geometric characteristics of MAU3-60 propeller

r /R	C/D	P/D	Skew	Rake/D	t /D	f /D
0.2	0.174	1.455	0.000	0.0	0.0434	0.0430
0.25	0.202	1.444	2.328	0.0	0.0396	0.0395
0.3	0.229	1.433	4.655	0.0	0.0358	0.0370
0.4	0.275	1.412	9.633	0.0	0.0294	0.0344
0.5	0.312	1.361	13.948	0.0	0.0240	0.0305
0.6	0.337	1.285	18.378	0.0	0.0191	0.0247
0.7	0.347	1.200	22.747	0.0	0.0146	0.0199
0.8	0.334	1.112	27.145	0.0	0.0105	0.0161
0.9	0.280	1.027	31.575	0.0	0.0067	0.0134
0.95	0.210	0.985	33.788	0.0	0.0048	0.0140
1.0	0.000	0.942	36.000	0.0	0.0029	-

Number of blades, 3; expended area ratio, 0.6; design advanced coefficient, 0.5.

The number of structural mesh is 12×12 and of the fluid mesh is 8×8 for every blade. The results appear in Fig 2 ~ 5, for thrust coefficient K_T , pitch ratio P/D and camber distribution C . General agreement between the present approach and PSF2 (Propeller Steady Flow) [11] analysis in the region of high advanced coefficient J ($J=V_a/nD$, V_a : advance velocity of ship, n : rotation speed of propeller), leads to the conclusion that the present nonlinear approach is satisfactory for calculating the response of a propeller blade. The stacking sequence effects on thrust are shown in Fig. 2. The thrust of composite propeller with stacking sequence of $[0/90/-\theta_2]_s$ are very close to the results of PSF2, in which a rigid structure is considered. Due to the stacking sequence effects, the thrust of composite propeller with $[0/90/\theta_2]_s$ are larger than those with $[0/90/-\theta_2]_s$ in region of low advanced coefficient. The larger of the angle θ , the higher the thrust increases. Fig. 3 and 4 show the variation of pitch ratio in different locations and different advanced coefficients. The pitch variation increases of blades with $[0/90/-\theta_2]_s$ and decreases with $[0/90/\theta_2]_s$. The higher of the pitch is, the larger the thrust. Therefore the phenomena of variation of pitch may use to describe the variation of thrust of composite blade with different stacking sequences. The camber of the blade dose not vary much in the blade, its maximal variation occurs near the tip of the blade. Hydroelastic effects have been shown to influence the performance of composite propeller and can improve the numerical results.

CONCLUSIONS

A geometrical non-linear finite element method coupled with analysis of a non-cavitating lifting surface was used to assess the performance of a composite marine propeller blades. The hydroelastic behavior of the propeller with unbalanced stacking sequences of $[0/90/\theta_2]_s$ and $[0/90/-\theta_2]_s$ were investigated and discussed. Stacking sequences effects have been shown to influence the thrust, pitch ratio and camber of composite propeller blades, especially, in region of low advanced coefficient.

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Figure 1: The projected view of MAU3-60 propeller

Figure 2: The thrust coefficient characteristics of the MAU3-60 propeller

Figure 3: Pitch variation of blade with $[0/90/30_2]_s$

Figure 4: Pitch variation of blade with $[0/90/-30_2]_s$